

Phase Behavior and Dissociation Kinetics of Lamins in a Polymer Model of Progeria

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One of the key structural proteins in the eukaryotic cell nucleus is lamin. Lamins can assemble into a two-dimensional protein meshwork at the nuclear periphery, known as the nuclear lamina, which provides rigidity and shape to the nucleus. Mutations in lamin proteins that alter the structure of the nuclear lamina underlie laminopathic diseases, including Hutchinson–Gilford Progeria Syndrome (HGPS). Experiments have shown that, compared to healthy cells, lamin supramolecular structures (e.g., protofilaments) assemble into a thicker lamina in HGPS, where they form highly stable nematic microdomains at the nuclear periphery, reminiscent of liquid crystals. This significantly alters the morphological and mechanical properties of the nucleus. In this study, we investigate the aggregation of lamin fibrous structures and their dissociation kinetics from the nuclear periphery by modeling them as coarse-grained, rod-like polymer chains confined within a rigid spherical shell. Our model reproduces the formation of multidirectional nematic domains at the nuclear surface and the reduced lamin dissociation observed in HGPS nuclei by adjusting lamin concentration, lamin-lamin (head-tail), and lamin-shell association strengths. While nematic phase formation requires relatively strong lamin-shell affinity under any non-vanishing inter-lamin attraction, the thickness of the lamina layer is primarily controlled by head-tail association strength in the model. Furthermore, the unbinding kinetics of lamin chains from the lamina exhibit a concentration-dependent facilitated dissociation, suppressed by strong intra-lamin interactions, reminiscent of diseased nuclei. Overall, our calculations reveal the physical mechanisms by which mutations affecting native lamin interactions and concentration could lead to an abnormal nuclear lamina in laminopathic diseases.

Keywords: laminopathies, nucleus, progeria, coarse-grained simulations, rod-like polymers

I. INTRODUCTION

The nuclear lamina is a two-dimensional meshwork structure mainly composed of lamin proteins that are type V intermediate filaments [1–4]. The lamina is located at the nuclear periphery, underneath the inner nuclear membrane (INM)—phospholipid bilayer of the nuclear envelope that faces the nucleoplasm—and maintains the shape and structural integrity of eukaryotic cell nuclei [5–10]. Nuclear lamina can disassemble during the nuclear envelope breakdown stage of cell division into its molecular components and re-assembling around the decondensing chromosomes at the end of the replication [11, 12]. This intricate process requires constituting lamin proteins to self-organize repeatedly and accurately at the nuclear periphery without interfering with the functional and mechanical properties of the nucleus.

The mammalian lamina comprises two main types of lamin proteins: A/C and B [2, 8]. Both lamin types share common structural features: a short N-terminal head domain, an α -helical central rod domain, and a globular tail domain [13–15]. The first level of structural assembly of lamin proteins is the formation of a dimer. This occurs when the central rod domains of two lamins coil in a parallel fashion [2, 14–16]. Dimers can further associate with

one another to form high-aspect ratio fibrous structures (e.g., protofilaments) [14, 15, 17] (see Supplementary Material Fig S1). Lamin fibers of various lengths and diameters sterically interact with each other and INM [15, 18]. These reversible interactions allow lamin supramolecular structures to localize near the nuclear periphery, around the chromosomes, and form the nuclear lamina meshwork underneath the INM [13, 19, 20]. Both *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies suggest that the lamina is a relatively isotropic, heterogeneous network of lamin fibers in healthy cells, exhibiting polymer-network characteristics [21, 22] and "node" distributions [17, 22, 23]. Notably, in most healthy cells, lamin distribution at the nuclear lamina appears uniform at the scale of several microns under fluorescence microscopy [8, 22].

The molecular structure of the lamina is altered in a class of diseases collectively known as laminopathies. One such disease is Hutchinson–Gilford Progeria Syndrome (HGPS), also briefly referred to as progeria, a rare genetic disease that causes the onset of premature aging [6, 8, 24–29]. The main cause of HGPS is a single-point mutation in the *LMNA* gene that encodes human lamin A [30–32]. This mutation produces a truncated form of lamin A (i.e., progerin), which lacks 50 amino acids at the tail domain. Progerin remains permanently farnesylated following post-translational modifications, unlike wild-type (*wt*) lamin A [24, 25, 27, 33–35]. Farnesylation can enhance hydrophobic interactions, promoting a stronger binding tendency of progerin towards

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FIG. 1. The schematics of the MD simulation model and simulation steps. (A) Coarse-grained lamin fiber with terminal head, tail, and central hydrophobic region. The terminal (head and tail) domains are allowed to associate with one another and are marked with the same color for simplification. (B-C) Illustration of the MD simulation steps. (B) The initial structure is minimized for 10^4 MD time steps. (C) After minimization, the head-tail association potential, U_{HT} , and lamin-shell interaction, U_{LN} , are switched on, and the simulations are run for another 10^6 MD time steps.

the INM or other hydrophobic components of the lamina. These alterations, in turn, could lead to anomalies in the morphology and mechanical properties of cell nuclei, significantly decreasing cell viability in the disease [20, 36, 37].

In the progression of HGPS, as the nuclear concentration of mutant lamin A increases, the nucleus becomes mechanically more rigid and morphologically distorted [34, 38–43]. Polarization light microscopy experiments further elucidated that lamins fibers form orientally ordered, uncorrelated nematic domains in the nuclear lamina of HGPS cells, each large enough to display birefringence [7]. On the contrary, no birefringent pattern was observed at the lamina of healthy nuclei, suggesting the presence of randomly oriented lamin filaments [7, 41, 44]. Notably, studies also suggest that both wt lamin A and progerin can form paracrystalline phases *in vitro* [15, 36], a property encountered in solutions of rod-like molecules with high bending rigidity (e.g., liquid crystals) [45–47]. Notably, when confined by convex spherical surfaces, short (i.e., compared to the dimensions of the confining shell) polymer chains with high bending rigidity (e.g., rod-like) exhibit nematic phases in molecular simulations [48–51]. This, combined with the available experimental data, indicates that the formation of nematic phase domains observed in nuclei of most laminopathic cells could result from irregular biomolecular interactions promoting increased localization of mutant lamins to the nuclear periphery.

Experiments further suggest that the dissociation properties of lamin proteins are altered in HGPS cells. Photobleaching experiments have shown that nucleoplasmic and peripheral lamins exchange with one another in healthy cells [7], further confirming that lamins can interact transiently with the lamina [52, 53]. In contrast to a healthy lamina, in HGPS, mutant lamins are irreversibly associated with the INM, exhibiting much weaker exchange kinetics with its nucleoplasmic coun-

terparts compared to *wt*-lamin A and significantly depleted from nucleoplasm [7, 26]. These findings indicate a potential correlation between lamina’s structural and kinetic properties in disease.

Overall, experimental evidence suggests that lamin proteins’ assembly and organization in the nuclear lamina are affected by lamin concentration and lamin affinity toward one another or the INM. Nevertheless, these factors’ relative biophysical roles in determining the nuclear lamina’s micro-scale properties, particularly in disease phenotypes, are poorly understood. While a limited number of computational studies provide insights into the formation of misshapen nuclei, such as those observed in HGPS [9, 54], exploring physical interactions and stoichiometric conditions that can lead to the multidirectional nematic domains, thicker lamina, and suppressed dissociation in laminopathies can help decipher the physical principles of the disease progression.

While the nuclear lamina is a highly complex biomolecular structure, the formation of this protein meshwork in healthy cells requires: i) lamin localization near the INM [8]; ii) relatively stable association of lamins with one another to form polymer-network-like structures [22, 23]; iii) sufficient lamin concentration to occupy around $50 \pm 10\%$ of the inner nuclear surface [17]. In this work, to study primary mechanisms involved in lamina assembly, we consider lamin supramolecular structures as rod-like polymer chains confined in a spherical shell representing the nuclear void and perform coarse-grained molecular dynamics (MD) calculations (Fig. 1). Focusing particularly on the effect of chain concentration, inter-association strength between lamin chains, and chain-shell interactions, we emulate the formation of nematic phase domains and lamina thickening reported in HGPS. We also correlate slow lamin dissociation and lamina thickening observed in diseased nuclei. Our study suggests that the concentration alone cannot dictate lamin exchange kinetics or nuclear lamina thickening. Instead,

there needs to be a compromise between the strength of the inter-lamin association and the interaction of lamin fibers with the INM to observe structural anomalies in the nuclear lamina structure.

II. METHODS

A. Molecular model of nuclear lamins

In nucleoplasm, individual lamin proteins are not solvated but rather exist in their dimer form [2, 8]. On the contrary, lamins dimers typically aggregate near the nuclear boundary as more complex fibrous structures (e.g., protofilaments) with high-aspect ratios, leading to an average lamina thickness of 14 ± 2 nm and a mean fiber length of 380 ± 122 nm [17, 43]. Thus, in our study, each lamin fiber is approximated as a Kremer-Grest (KG) rod-like, bead-spring chain in implicit solvent (Fig. 1A) [55].

Given that HGPS and other laminopathies are predominantly associated with mutations in A-type lamins rather than B-type, we focus on modeling a single type of lamin fiber [30]. A-type lamins also play a key role in regulating the nuclear shape and stiffness [28, 31, 56]. Each lamin chain consists of head and tail domains, modeling the terminal ends of lamin fibers. The central beads model hydrophobic interactions at the core of lamin fibers and head and tail beads repel or attract each other (Fig. 1A). The beads representing the head, tail, and central hydrophobic region are all the same size. Each lamin fiber consists of $n = 8$ beads unless otherwise specified. Using shorter or longer chains (i.e., $n = 4$ or $n = 16$) does not affect the results qualitatively (see Supplementary Material Fig. S2-S7). The lamin fibers are confined within a rigid spherical boundary to mimic the steric effect of the nuclear envelope (Fig. 1C). The spherical confinement has a radius, $R_0 = 34\sigma$, unless specified otherwise (Fig. 1). Here, the bead size is set to $b = 1\sigma$, which defines the unit length scale in simulations.

The concentration of lamin proteins (monomeric) was reported to be around > 100 nM *in vivo* [57]. Hence, it is difficult to estimate the quantity of lamin fibers (composed of many monomers) accumulating near the periphery. Thus, we calculate a polymer physical quantity, a 2-dimensional analog of concentration for fibers, by assuming a nuclear diameter of $d \approx 10$ μm and an approximate lamin fiber length of $l \approx 400$ nm [5, 56, 58] and estimate the number of lamins required to cover the surface of as $N \approx (10 \mu\text{m}/4 \times 10^2 \text{ nm})^2 \approx 10^3$. To probe various concentration regimes, we vary lamin fiber concentration, c , by increasing the number of rods within our rigid, spherical nucleus model between $N = 500$ and $N = 4000$, covering between 50% to over 100% of the surface area of the confinement to account for the accumulation of progerin in HGPS nuclei and nucleoplasmic lamins in healthy cells [8, 17, 26]. This range also corresponds to lamin concentrations above and below the bulk overlap concentration, c^* (Eqn. 1), which determines the transi-

tion of a polymer solution from a dilute to a semi-dilute regime. The threshold concentration, c^* , marks where individual lamin chains begin to overlap and interact with one another sterically and is defined as

$$c^* = \frac{n}{v} \quad (1)$$

where $v \approx l^3 \approx n^3 \sigma^3$ is the pervaded volume of a single lamin rod. The overlap concentration for 8-bead lamin rods, $n = 8$, is $c^* \approx 0.03\sigma^{-3}$. The concentration values used in the simulations are shown in Table I. We discuss our results by either using absolute concentration, c , with the units σ^{-3} , or concentration normalized by c^* . Notably, $c = 1.6c^*$ i.e. $c \approx c^*$, also corresponds to an occupied lamina volume of 13.5% in our simulations (Fig. 4) [17].

TABLE I. The total number of lamin chains, N , and concentrations, c , used in MD simulations.

N	$c(\sigma^{-3})$	c/c^*
500	0.02	0.8
750	0.04	1.2
1000	0.05	1.6
1250	0.06	2.0
1500	0.07	2.4
2000	0.097	3.3
2500	0.12	4.0
3000	0.15	4.8
3500	0.17	5.6
4000	0.19	6.5

B. Simulation setup

In MD simulations, lamin rods are initially placed randomly within the spherical confinement (Fig. 1B). We verify that the initial configuration does not affect simulation results (see Supplementary Material Fig. S8). Initial configurations are minimized for 10^4 MD steps (Fig. 1B) using an integration time step of $\Delta t = 0.001\tau$, where τ is the unit of time in the simulations. Following the minimization, each system is run for an additional 10^6 MD steps with $\Delta t = 0.005\tau$, allowing the system to reach equilibrium (Supplementary Material Fig. S9). During the data production simulations, attractive lamin-shell and lamin-lamin interactions are introduced to emulate healthy and diseased nuclear lamina phenotypes (Fig. 1C). The spherical confinement exerts an attractive potential, U_{LN} , mimicking the interaction between the lamin fibers and the nuclear periphery (e.g., with the INM) (Fig. 1C). Since lamin proteins can assemble via head-tail interactions [2, 15], the head domain of each lamin fiber interacts exclusively with the tail domain of other lamins through with a strength of U_{HT} (Fig. 1A).

FIG. 2. Isotropic and nematic phase formation of lamin chains at the inner surface of the shell. (A–C) Representative snapshots of the rigid, model nucleus at various head-to-tail association potentials, U_{HT} , at a lamin concentrations of $c =$ (A) $0.8c^*$, (B) $1.6c^*$, and (C) $3.3c^*$ at a fixed lamin-shell interaction strength, $U_{LN} = 10.0k_B T$. (D) Percentage of lamin rod pairs aligned parallel to each other as a function of concentration, c , for various head-tail association strengths, U_{HT} . (E) Percentage of peripheral lamin chains within a distance of 2.5σ from the inner surface for various head-tail attraction strengths, U_{HT} .

The non-bonded, steric interactions between chain beads and/or with the inner confining surface are modeled by using the Lennard-Jones (LJ) potential

$$V(r_{ij}) = 4\epsilon \left[\left(\frac{\sigma}{r_{ij}} \right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma}{r_{ij}} \right)^6 \right] \quad \text{for } r \leq r_c, \quad (2)$$

where ϵ represents the energy unit, r_{ij} is the distance between two beads, and r_c is the cut-off distance beyond which the LJ potential becomes negligible. For attractive interactions, such as head-tail and lamin-shell interactions, r_c is set to 2.5σ . For all other interactions, the cut-off radius is set to $r_c = 2^{1/6}\sigma$ to ensure steric repulsion. The default value of the interaction strength in Eq. 2 is $\epsilon = 1k_B T$, where k_B is the Boltzmann constant and T is the reduced absolute temperature. The attraction between the head and tail beads of lamin chains, U_{HT} , as well as between lamins and the confining, structureless, surface, U_{LN} , is adjusted by increasing ϵ in Eq. 2. Since affinities for lamin structures are not known, to probe various affinity ranges for U_{HT} and U_{LN} , we vary attraction strengths as low as several $k_B T$ (susceptible to thermal fluctuations with energies on the order of $k_B T$), and as high as $U_{LN} = 10.0k_B T$. These attraction ranges are consistent with previous models with similar coarse-graining levels [59, 60].

All bonded interactions between adjacent beads in each lamin fiber are described using a Finitely Extensible Non-linear Elastic (FENE) potential

$$V_{\text{Bond}}(r_{ij}) = -0.5k r_{ij}^2 \ln \left[1 - \left(\frac{r_{ij}}{r_0} \right)^2 \right], \quad (3)$$

where the bond energy is set to $k = 30.0k_B T/\sigma^2$ and the maximum bond distance is set to $r_0 = 1.5\sigma$.

The bending fluctuations of lamin chains are constrained by a harmonic angle potential in the form of

$$V_{\text{Bend}}(\theta) = k_\theta(\theta - \theta_0)^2, \quad (4)$$

where the bending energy is set to $k_\theta = 10.0k_B T/\text{rad}^2$, and the reference angle is $\theta_0 = \pi$. These parameters result in a persistence length higher than the length of each lamin chain, $l_p > l$, ensuring that they behave predominantly as rod-like polymers in simulations (Supplementary Material Fig. S10).

All MD simulations are performed under constant particle number N , constant volume V , and constant temperature T , using a Langevin thermostat (see Supplementary Material for further details). Simulations are carried out in the LAMMPS MD simulations package [61]. Various Python libraries are used for data anal-

ysis [62]. VMD and OVITO were used for structural visualization [63, 64]. In all graphs and analyses presented below, we omit error bars when they are smaller than the symbol size.

C. Kinetic calculations

To quantify the kinetics of lamin chains in simulations, we monitor the dissociation of peripherally localized chains for various binding affinities (U_{HT} and U_{LN}) and lamin concentrations. Specifically, we measure the decay of the population of peripherally *bound* lamin fibers, while those freely diffusing in the bulk of the confinement (i.e., nucleoplasm) are considered *unbound*. As the simulation progresses, the initially bound lamins, n_0 , dissociate and exchange with those in the nucleoplasm. The number of remaining bound lamins, $n(t)$, is calculated as a function of the time, t (Supplementary Material Fig. S11). A lamin is considered dissociated and tagged as unbound if it moves beyond a defined cut-off radius, R_C , from the nuclear periphery. If a dissociated lamin protein rebinds to the spherical confinement, it is not counted again as part of the surviving lamins, $n(t)$. The dissociation cut-off distance is set to the size of a single chain, $R_0 < R_C \leq 8\sigma$ [60, 65] (see Supplementary Material Fig. S12). We also calculate the time-averaged concentration of *unbound*, free lamins, c_{free} , as the average number of lamin rods that remain unbound over simulation time (Supplementary Material). For the analysis, only the last half of each simulation is considered. A single-exponential function is used to fit the dissociation data to determine off-rates

$$\frac{n(t)}{n_0} = a + b \exp(-k_{off}t), \quad (5)$$

where $n_0 = n(t=0)$ and k_{off} is the off-rate with the units of inverse time. a and b are fitting parameters normalized such that $a + b = 1$ at $t = 0$, where a corresponds to the fraction of permanently bound lamins as $t \rightarrow \infty$. If all initially bound chains become unbound, $a = 0$ and $b = 1$. In a subset of cases, not all initially bound lamins dissociate and start permanently bound to the confining wall. As a result, $a < 1$, leading to a long-time plateau for surface-bound lamins in the survival fraction data. The fit is specifically applied when the bound lamin fraction satisfies $n(t)/n_0 \leq 0.5$, ensuring that it can capture the decay time of dissociation.

III. RESULTS

In our simulations, most lamin chains localize near the spherical boundary at $t > 0$, forming a layer of adsorbed chains (Fig. 1C). We will refer to this layer as “lamina” throughout this work. Once some or all of the chains are localized to the periphery, this is followed by either lamin

dissociation or stable accumulation of chains to the spherical boundary depending on the lamin concentration, c , head-to-tail association strength, U_{HT} , and the interaction strength of lamin rods with the interior surface of the spherical confinement, U_{LN} .

A. Nematic phase domains of lamin chains appear above the threshold concentration, c^*

To explore the molecular conditions affecting the molecular organization of lamin proteins in the nuclear lamina assembly, we first analyze the effect of lamin chain concentration in our simulations. We scan the concentrations above and below the threshold concentration, c^* , (Eq. 1), where lamin chains can be at steric contact in the bulk, $0.8c^* \leq c \leq 3.3c^*$ (Table I). Since we compare two interactions in our model, U_{LN} and U_{HT} , we investigate their relative contribution to the nuclear lamina assembly process systematically. To do so, we first choose a high lamin-shell interaction strength, $U_{LN} = 10.0k_B T$, while varying the head-tail association potential (Fig. 2). This ensures the localization of lamin chains near the boundary of the spherical confinement while allowing us to interrogate the effects of specific attractions between lamin chains. We will discuss the effects of the surface attraction in the next section further.

Fig. 2 shows representative snapshots taken from the final stage of different simulations at various concentrations. These simulations reveal that concentration directly affects the morphology of lamin phases localized at the inner surface of the model nucleus, particularly when lamin chains have a strong affinity towards the confining boundary (i.e., $U_{LN} = 10.0k_B T$). At low concentrations (i.e., $c \leq c^*$), lamin chains are arranged with no specific directional order regardless of the head-tail attraction strength (Fig. 2A, top to bottom). Notably, increasing the head-tail association strength does not affect their isotropic orientation but promotes the formation of nodes, leading to a network configuration on the surface (Fig. 2A, bottom). At intermediate to high concentrations, $c \geq c^*$, nematic phase domains appear and cover the entire inner surface of the spherical confinement (Fig. 2B). These phases become more distinct as the inter-lamin affinity is increased further, independent of U_{HT} (Fig. 2C, top to bottom). Importantly, these nematic phases visually differ from global phases of semi-flexible chains reported earlier [49–51] and are visually non-percolating and consistent with the nematically ordered domains reported *in vivo* and *in vitro* for progeria nuclei [6, 7, 36].

To further characterize the formation of nematic phase domains on the surface in a more quantitative way, we attempt to use methodologies previously used to study nematic liquid crystalline phases of semi-flexible polymers [48, 66]. Accordingly, the largest eigenvalue of the diagonalized configurational tensor calculated over all chains can describe whether all chains align parallel

FIG. 3. Representative simulation snapshots of the exterior of the shell for various values of U_{LN} and U_{HT} at a concentration, $c = 2.0c^*$. (A-C) From top to bottom, U_{LN} increases, and U_{HT} increases from left to right. Only those chains within a distance of 2.5σ from the surface are shown, while those in the interior of the confinement are not shown for clarity.

to each other (i.e., a “global” nematic order) in bulk or on a spherical surface [48–51]. However, in our systems, where the surface is covered by randomly oriented nematic domains (Fig. 2), the largest eigenvalue is close to zero. Hence, it cannot distinguish between locally ordered domains and a global isotropic (i.e., all chains are randomly oriented on the surface). Thus, we calculate a spin-spin-like order parameter instead, such that if a chain aligns next to its nearest neighbor, the order parameter is $|S| = 1$ or; otherwise, $S = 0$. Averaging over pairs obeying the nearest neighbor criterium ($r_{nn} < 1.5\sigma$) demonstrates the dependence of lamin ordering on the concentration and head-tail affinity (Fig. 2D). Contrarily, the amount of lamins chain localized to the periphery decreases with increasing concentration, particularly for weak inter-lamin attraction (Fig. 2E). This suggests that strong surface affinity and lamin-lamin attraction are required for the peripheral accumulation of chains in nematic phases (see Supplementary material Fig. S13). Notably, we observe similar alignment trends for shorter lamin fibers (see Supplementary material Fig. S14 and S15). Overall, our calculations demonstrate that concen-

trations above c^* could lead to nematic phase domains once lamin chains are localized to the inner nuclear surface.

B. Nematic phase formation on the shell surface is a result of the competition between lamin-lamin and lamin-shell interactions

Having demonstrated nematic phase formation under strong peripheral localization of lamin chains (i.e., $U_{LN} \geq U_{HT}$) (Fig. 2), we next explore whether a weaker U_{LN} can affect the phase formation. In this investigation, a concentration slightly above our intermediate concentration (i.e., $c = 2.0c^*$) is chosen to ensure that we observe nematic phases .

Fig. 3 shows surface configurations of lamin chains for various interaction schemes: from left to right, the lamin-lamin (head-tail) attraction, U_{HT} , is increased, while from top to bottom, lamin-shell attraction, U_{LN} , is increased in separate simulations. The weakest lamin-shell association strength used here (i.e., $U_{LN} = 2.5k_B T$) leads

FIG. 4. The effect of the ratio of affinities, U_{HT}/U_{LN} , concentration, c , and chain length, n , on lamina thickness. (A) The methodology used to calculate lamina thickness, δ , from simulation trajectories. The schematic shows the fluctuation of radial coordinates for a single *bound* and *unbound* lamin. A lamin is considered *bound* to the shell if its radial coordinate stops fluctuating significantly during a simulation. (B) Lamina thickness, δ , vs. concentration as a function of c^* , c , at various affinity ratios and chain lengths. (C) Lamina thickness, δ , vs. absolute lamin concentration for various U_{HT}/U_{LN} . (D-E) Radial probability distributions, $p(r)$, as a function of radial distance, r .

to either isotropic chain organization or a disrupted network with unidirectional domains in between, depending on the strength of head-tail attraction (Fig. 3A, left to right). Notably, this effect is observed for shorter and longer chains as well (see Supplementary Material Fig. S16 and S17). As the inter-lamin attraction is increased, some nematic domains of loosely packed chains also emerge (Fig. 3A, center and right). However, a lamin-lamin attraction stronger than the surface binding affinity (i.e., $U_{HT} \gg U_{LN}$) enhances bulk aggregation and reduces surface localization, leading to bundled chain structures on the surface (Fig. 3A, right).

The intermediate value of lamin-shell attraction strengths tested here (i.e., $U_{LN} = 5.0k_B T$) is also sufficient to align the chains parallel to one another (Fig. 3B and Supplementary material Fig. S18 and S19). However, in these cases, sparse lamin-free regions (see Supplementary material Fig. S19) and bulk accumulation (Supplementary material Fig. S20) also emerge, particularly if the lamin-lamin attraction is stronger than the lamin-shell attraction. As the lamin-shell association strength is increased further to $U_{LN} = 10.0k_B T$, this trend disappears, and lamin chains cover the entire surface symmetrically, irrespective of the strength of head-tail attraction (Fig. 3C).

Overall, these comparative simulations suggest that mutations increasing lamin association with INM could be pivotal for accumulating lamin chains near the periphery. Nevertheless, such a pattern can be distorted if the

lamin-lamin attraction excessively overcomes lamin-shell attraction, causing bulk aggregation. In the next sections, we will discuss how these interactions might govern the effective thickness of the lamin (rod) layer at the periphery and the dissociation kinetics of chains from this layer.

C. Thickness of the lamin layer depends on lamin-lamin association strength and concentration

Previous experimental studies reported thicker nuclear lamina in disease phenotypes due to lamin accumulation towards the periphery [8, 22, 67]. Consistently, our analyses in the previous sections demonstrate that lamin chains can coat the inner surface of the spherical confinement (Fig. 2, 3, and Supplementary Material Fig. S21 and S22). To quantify the thickness of the lamina layer in our simulations, we analyze the radial distributions of the lamin chains in the model spherical nucleus. We calculate the positional fluctuations, dr , of the center-of-mass-adjusted radial distances for each chain over the simulation time. As the simulation proceeds, if the radial coordinate of a chain fluctuates weakly (i.e., less than the unit size of a bead, $dr \leq 0.25$) near the shell boundary, the lamin chain is considered immobile and *bound* (Fig. 4A). The time-averaged radial position, R , of this chain contributes to the thickness of the nuclear lamina

via the expression:

$$\delta = R_0 - \langle R \rangle, \quad (6)$$

where R_0 is the radius of spherical confinement (Fig. 1C), and $\langle R \rangle$ is the average radial position of all lamin chains fulfilling the *bound* condition.

Fig. 4 shows the thickness of the lamin layer, calculated via Eq. 6, as a function of concentration for various ratios of head-tail to lamin-shell affinities, U_{HT}/U_{LN} . In addition to our default chain size (i.e., $n = 8$), calculation results for shorter chains (i.e., $n = 4$) are also shown in Fig. 4 (also see Supplementary Material Fig. S23 and S24). As a general trend, the thickness of the chain layer at the periphery δ increases with increasing concentration, regardless of chain length n (Fig. 4B and C). The thickness of the lamina layer also increases with the relative increase of inter-lamin affinity as compared to the lamin-shell attraction U_{HT}/U_{LN} (Fig. 4B, C). For relatively weak inter-lamin attraction (i.e., $U_{HT}/U_{LN} < 1$, this increase is weak but statistically significant and consistent with experiments where the peripheral accumulation of mutated lamin A increases with the progression of HGPS [8, 43, 57].

Notably, the concentration also determines the effect of competition between inter-lamin and lamin-shell interaction. At the lowest concentration used here (i.e., $c < c^*$), the number of lamin chains in the spherical confinement is only enough to form a single layer with a maximum thickness $\delta \approx 1.3\sigma$, irrespective of the affinity ratio, concentration or chain length n (Fig. 4B and Supplementary Material Fig. S25). At intermediate (i.e., $c \approx c^*$) to high (i.e., $c \gg c^*$) concentrations, the thickness becomes dependent on the ratio of the two competing interactions U_{HT}/U_{LN} . For $U_{HT}/U_{LN} < 1$, the thickness has visually no dependence on concentration (Fig. 4B). Notably, at such ratios, there are unbound, freely diffusing chains in bulk (see Fig. 5A). As the ratio U_{HT}/U_{LN} is increased above the unity, the effect of concentration becomes more dominant, resulting in the formation of chain multilayers covering the entire surface (Fig. 4B and C, 5A and Supplementary Material Fig. S25).

To further confirm the partitioning of lamin proteins into *bound* (i.e., those forming the layer) and *unbound* (i.e., free or nucleoplasmic) phases, we also calculate the radial probability distributions, $p(r)$, by counting the number of lamin chains, $n(r)$, in a thin slice of the shell's volume with width $\Delta r = 1.0\sigma$:

$$p(r) = \frac{n(r)}{4\pi R_0^2 \Delta r}. \quad (7)$$

The radial probability distribution for various affinity ratios is consistent with the thickness calculations (Fig. 4D, E). At low lamin-lamin interaction strengths with fixed $U_{LN} = 10.0k_B T$, specifically $U_{HT}/U_{LN} = 0.25$, the nuclear lamins are distributed throughout the confinement, co-existing in both the central and peripheral regions of the volume (Fig. 4D and E). In contrast, at higher lamin-lamin affinities (i.e., $U_{HT}/U_{LN} = 1.0$), lamin chains localize at the periphery, leaving the bulk lamin-free (Fig. 4D

and E). Notably, larger error bars in $U_{HT}/U_{LN} > 1$ case for both chain lengths are consistent with the non-uniform chain distribution and larger thickness of the layer at the periphery (see Supplementary Material Fig. S25). Collectively, these calculations demonstrate that while weak lamin-shell association can localize some lamin proteins at the periphery, the accumulation of lamin chains to the periphery is primarily controlled by head-tail association affinity in the model. In diseased nuclei, this interaction could contribute to the partial thickening of the nuclear lamina.

D. Extent of lamin chain dissociation depends on head-tail association strength and concentration

Another hallmark of HGPS is the suppressed kinetic dissociation of mutant lamins from the nuclear lamina [7]. In accordance with those studies, in some of our simulations, lamin chains unbind from and rebind to the periphery. In other cases, they are more stably bound to the peripheral aggregates (Fig. 5 and Supplementary Material Fig. S25). To quantify lamin dissociation kinetics thoroughly in our simulations, we calculate the survival fraction of bound lamins as a function of normalized simulation time, t , for various concentration and affinity cases (see Methods Section). For simplicity, we choose a fixed lamin-shell attraction strength, $U_{LN} = 10.0k_B T$, and vary the head-tail attraction of lamin fibers. However, reducing the strength of lamin-shell attraction from $U_{LN} = 10.0k_B T$ or reducing chain length (i.e., $n = 4$) does not change the overall lamin dissociation patterns qualitatively as discussed below (see Supplementary Material Fig. S26-S30).

Fig. 4A shows that, for relatively weaker lamin-lamin affinity (i.e., $U_{HT}/U_{LN} = 0.25$ with $U_{HT} = 2.5k_B T$), as the chain concentration is increased, more free lamins are observed in bulk. Furthermore, increasing the concentrations leads to a more rapid decay in the survival fractions (Fig. 5A, right panel): more than half of the bound lamins dissociate within the first half of the simulation time as the concentration is increased at $c > c^*$ (Fig. 5A, right). Such a concentration-dependent dissociation pattern is consistent with the facilitated dissociation (FD) response, where an increase in the concentration of competing species in solution can lead to higher off-rates (i.e., shorter residence times) [60, 65, 68, 69] (see Supplementary Material Fig. S1 and S11). Accordingly, if there is an excess concentration of free nucleoplasmic lamins, they could compete with *bound* lamins at the nuclear lamina and speed up their dissociation.

Since the interaction affinities can affect FD [65], we extract off-rates from the dissociation data for various inter-lamin and lamin-shell affinities. We extract off-rates by fitting survival fraction data to the exponential function in Eq. 5 [69]. Interestingly, at high concentrations (i.e., $c \gg c^*$) where we observe consirable chain aggregation at the periphery, the calculated off-rates mostly

FIG. 5. Dependence of lamin dissociation kinetics on concentration, c , and head-to-tail association potential to lamin-shell affinity, U_{HT} . Yellow chains represent *unbound*, free lamin proteins participating in a kinetic exchange. (A) Illustrations representing the degree of lamin exchange at three different concentrations with fixed $U_{HT}/U_{LN} = 0.25$. The panel on the right shows the normalized survival fraction, $n(t)/n_0$, of *bound* nuclear lamins over time, t . (B) Off-rates as a function of head-to-tail association strength, U_{HT} , for various values of U_{LN} at a concentration $c = 5.6c^*$. (C) Representative snapshots and off-rates as a function of free lamin concentration for $U_{HT}/U_{LN} = 0.25$ for various lamin chain lengths, n .

depend on head-tail association affinity U_{HT} , visually independent of the lamin-shell attraction strength U_{LN} in simulations (Fig. 5B).

We next determine the effect of chain length on the kinetic exchange (Fig. 5C). Our calculations show that increasing the chain size, n , also requires more lamin chains to observe a similar amount of *free* chains in bulk, c_{free} (Fig. 5C, right panel). Nevertheless, we observe qualitatively similar patterns in lamin dissociation for comparable c_{free} values regardless of chain length. In general, off-rates increase monotonically with c_{free} at low concentrations, eventually approaching a saturation limit at higher ones, consistent with FD kinetics (Fig. 5C, right). The FD mechanism that we observe in Fig. 5C can be described by the following empirical equation [69, 70]

$$k_{off} = k_{slow}^{(0)} + ck_1, \quad (8)$$

where $k_{slow}^{(0)}$ is the off-rate in the absence of competing species in solution, and k_1 is the time constant of the rate-limiting step, associated with the lifetime of the partial binding of chains to their binding sites. Notably, the above expression was validated in the context of protein-DNA interactions even at nanomolar concentration of competing species [69, 71].

Overall, our analyses and calculations imply that increasing lamin head-tail affinity could suppress the dissociation of lamin chains from their aggregates at the periphery, often accompanied by a thicker (nematic) lamina at the periphery. This is compatible with experimental observations of suppressed (mutant) lamin dissociation

from HGPS lamina [7].

IV. DISCUSSION

The nuclear lamina can adapt to changing physiochemical and mechanical conditions by altering the concentration and solvation properties of its main constituents, lamin proteins. In this study, we model supramolecular structures of lamin proteins as stiff, short polymer filaments. This over-simplification allows us to explore the physical principles and relative interactions that can lead to experimentally observed morphological and kinetic changes in lamin's (particularly A-type lamins) phase behavior associated with laminopathies such as accelerated aging (i.e., progeria). In our simulations, the spherical, rigid confinement represents the nuclear void bounded by the INM, which can interact with lamin proteins. The lamin model attempts to mimic the complex head-tail association of lamin fibers by incorporating asymmetric interactions between chain ends (Fig. 1). This coarse-grained model recapitulates the formation of nematic phase domain, lamina thickening, and suppressed dissociation kinetics of mutant lamin proteins observed in diseased cell nuclei [7, 8, 39, 43]. It also emulates certain properties of the nuclear lamina in healthy cells under relatively weaker lamin-INM interactions. Below, we will further discuss the potential implications of our calculations in the context of the structural biology of cell nuclei in health and disease.

A. Alterations in lamin localization to the nuclear periphery can lead to structural anomalies in nuclear lamina

Once cell division initiates, the nuclear lamina disassembles via a hyperphosphorylation mechanism and later re-assembles around the replicated chromosomes of the sister cells [11, 12]. A prerequisite for this re-assembly is the localization of some, if not all, lamin proteins (mostly lamin A/C since lamin B is often attached to INM) or their supramolecular structures to the nuclear periphery. This way, lamins can associate with one another and/or with the INM to form a lamina meshwork underneath the INM. Importantly, this self-assembled and dynamic meshwork must provide mechanical support to the nucleus while ensuring nuclear shape stability in a healthy cell.

In our simulations, the localization of rod-like lamin chains results from the competition between the lamin self-affinity and their tendency to bind to the periphery of the spherical shell (i.e., the INM) (Fig. 4). Lamin-shell affinity comparable to the lamin-lamin (head-to-tail) association strength ensures the formation of a uniformly distributed lamin layer at the periphery, where lamin chains organize in a more isotropic, network-like fashion, consistent with the lamin organization in healthy cells [7].

The nuclear lamina becomes thicker and mechanically more rigid in HGPS due to the excess aggregation of mutant lamin A, progerin, at the nuclear lamina [7, 41, 42], causing decreasing morphological adaptability in the disease. From a molecular perspective, progerin remains far-nesylated after post-translational modifications. Farnesylation promotes progerin's membrane association and enhances its thermodynamic stability compared to *wt*-lamin A [72, 73]. Notably, increased hydrophobic interactions have also been reported between the tail domain of progerin and INM proteins, such as SUN1 and Emerin [28]. These experiments collectively suggest that truncated lamin A might have a stronger tendency to associate with the INM compared to *wt*-lamin A. Our simulations support this, showing that strong lamin-shell attraction (i.e., strong binding to the INM) can lead to strong aggregation of chains towards the periphery (Fig. 2 and 3). Further, under a finite lamin-lamin association strength, the strong peripheral localization gives rise to nematic-phase domains in calculations, which were realized experimentally both *in vitro* [36, 74] and *in vivo* [7]. The lamin chains in our study are strongly adsorbed to the surface as we also characterize via 2nd-order Legendre polynomial analyses (see Supplementary Material Fig. S7, S15). Yet, this order disappears in bulk or as the surface adsorption decreases. Notably, despite strong asymmetric attraction between lamin fibers (i.e., in a head-tail manner), our results are consistent with phase formations of relatively short chains confined in a spherical confinement (i.e., $l = nb < R_0$) [66]. Contrarily, longer semi-flexible chains (i.e., $l \approx R_0$) form global, unidirectional nematic phases (see Supplementary Material Fig. S2, S6, S7) [48–51], supporting the notion that in HGPS, lamin fibers could be shorter than their healthy counterparts.

Moreover, the formation of nematic domains may require stronger hydrophobic interactions between lamins at the nuclear surface, which is often the case in liquid crystals [47, 75–78]. Studies on the crystal structure of progeria mutant *S143F* protein suggested the formation of X-shaped disulfide bonds in the central rod domains of progerin [18]. This implies that hydrophobic interactions can play a role in altering the morphology of the lamina meshwork [18, 73], possibly bringing cysteine residues of progerin molecules close to one another. In light of our results, which treat the lamin proteins as hydrophobic (except their head and tail domains), the enhanced hydrophobic interactions in HGPS could also contribute to the formation of nematic phase domains at the nuclear lamina.

B. Inter-lamin affinity can dictate nuclear lamina thickening

In addition to the formation of nematic domains, nuclear lamina thickening also serves as a key disease hallmark along with abnormal nuclear shape [6, 8, 24–29, 67].

Accordingly, as progerin concentration increases parallel to the disease progression, the nuclear lamina thickens as toxic mutant proteins accumulate at the periphery [8, 43]. Such aggregation can be promoted by an increase in the effective affinity of mutant lamins towards each other or the INM. This view is also consistent with the observed decrease in exchange rates of progerin [7], indicating an increase in the interaction energies between mutant proteins and their molecular environment. In line with this evidence, our simulations suggest that in HGPS, the thickening of the nuclear lamina near the periphery could be the result of an interplay between lamin localization and increasing lamin-lamin association (e.g., head-tail) as the nuclear concentration of mutant lamins increases (Fig. 4). In fact, relatively higher head-tail association strength readily results in thicker chain layer and chain aggregation in simulations, suggesting a dominant effect for inter-lamin interactions.

Consistent with this view, permanent farnesylation of progerin enhances its binding properties to the INM compared to *wt*-lamin A [73], as discussed earlier. However, the farnesyl group remains sequestered within a hydrophobic region in the tail domain unless physiological concentrations of divalent ions, such as Ca^{2+} , are present at the nuclear periphery [67]. Without calcium ions, the farnesyl group only acts as a reversible crosslink, temporarily associating with membrane proteins, but can still dissociate into the nucleoplasm, a characteristic of healthy nuclei [19, 73]. Calcium can induce a conformational change in progerin, opening up the tail domain's Ig-like fold and exposing the farnesyl group for molecular interactions. This exposure can facilitate stronger intermolecular interactions with other lamins (e.g., progerin and other unaltered lamins) and the INM [26, 67]. These experimental observations are consistent with our MD simulations, where nuclear lamins become constrained to the INM when both head-tail association and lamin-shell association strengths are high (i.e., $U_{HT} \geq U_{LN} > 1k_B T$) (Fig. 4), suggesting an intricate interplay of intermolecular interactions promoting lamina thickening at the nuclear periphery.

C. Dissociation kinetics of lamins from nuclear lamina can have a concentration dependence

Photobleaching experiments suggest that peripherally bound lamins could exchange with their nucleoplasmic counterparts in healthy cells [7]. One possible mechanism by which free lamins can influence the kinetics of lamin exchange between those in the nuclear lamina and nucleoplasm (free) in health could be facilitated dissociation (FD) [60, 68, 69, 79]. FD causes an increased exchange (dissociation) rate for a ligand attached to its binding site when free ligands are present in the solution. The mechanism is based on the molecular-scale competition between the two ligands at the binding site (such as a third lamin) (see Supplementary Material Fig. S1,

S11, S26-S30). Nucleoplasmic lamin proteins can likely compete with their bound counterparts in the nuclear lamina, leading to rapidly decaying signals observed in the experiments. Our simulations demonstrate such a concentration-dependent mechanism for lamin chains of varying sizes (Fig. 5). In contrast, the exchange rate drops in HGPS [7], possibly due to increasing intermolecular interactions between the mutant protein and the nuclear lamina and depletion of lamin from nucleoplasm. Consistently, our calculations show that increased lamin-lamin affinity reduces dissociation rates while promoting further lamin accumulation near the periphery and eventually affecting the thickness of the chain layer (Fig. 4 and 5). Furthermore, unlike HGPS cells, the accumulation of *wt* lamin proteins increases nuclear stability in some healthy cell lines [41, 42] and even correlates with decreased DNA double-strand breaks [42]. Thus, based on the available literature and our simulations, we speculate that lamin unbinding kinetics from the nuclear lamina could also have structural consequences, leading to either a highly adaptive, mechanically soft lamina or a highly stable but mechanically brittle one.

In summary, we employed a coarse-grained polymer model of lamin supramolecular structures to investigate the key physical interactions that can drive the abnormal self-assembly of lamin proteins in the formation of the nuclear lamina, with a particular focus on HGPS. Our findings suggest that enhanced intermolecular interactions among mutant lamins can lead to specific disease hallmarks in the nuclear lamina structure. Our simulations reveal an interplay between lamin-lamin and lamin-INM interactions in a concentration-dependent manner, demonstrating how this interplay could reduce lamin exchange rates, cause lamina thickening, and promote the formation of nematic microdomains on the lamina, as observed in HGPS.

D. Limitations of the lamin model

Although our coarse-grained model can recapitulate several experimental phenotypes observed in progeria, namely i) phase transition of the lamina from an isotropic to nematic organization, ii) lamina thickening, and iii) suppressed lamin dissociation kinetics between the lamina and interior, a conclusive understanding of lamina assembly and structure in disease is far from complete. We assume a uniformly attractive spherical confinement to model the INM. In reality, the INM exhibits spatially heterogeneous mechanical and biochemical properties [17, 22, 44, 53]. This spherical confinement is also rigid, unlike the eukaryotic nucleus, which undergoes significant shape distortions in diseases like progeria. Furthermore, given that the disease is caused by a *de novo* point mutation in the *LMNA* gene that encodes for human lamin A/C [20], our model focuses on a single lamin type only. On the contrary, the lamina meshwork in healthy cells is composed of

heterogeneous, network-like arrangements of both A- and B-type lamins [23]. Our model also oversimplifies the assembly of lamin supramolecular structures such as protofilaments and other higher-order structures by modeling lamin chains as a monodisperse solution of semi-flexible rods, ignoring dimers or monomeric lamins or their self-assembly. The model also does not include chromatin, which can affect lamin organization or *vice versa*. It simplifies overall parameters that might affect the nuclear lamina organization into concentration, inter-lamin, and lamin-shell interactions and ignores any specific interactions that can play key roles in disease. Future studies could benefit from more sophisticated models to better understand these experimental features such as distorted nuclear morphology and mechanics in HGPS [8, 29, 38–40]. For instance, replacing spherical confinement with elastic shell models [80, 81] filled with chromatin [54] could provide deeper insights into nuclear shape alterations associated with the disease.

V. SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

The supplementary material provides additional details on the MD simulations, benchmarking, and data analysis methods used to quantify results (Fig. 2, Fig. 4 and 5). It includes extended analyses for shorter and longer chains and figures for additional lamin concentration, inter-lamin, and lamin-shell attractions.

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